

Pattern Recognition in Financial Charts Using Image Segmentation Technique

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Abstract

Pattern recognition in financial markets plays a crucial role in technical analysis, aiding traders in making informed decisions. This study presents an approach to detect key market patterns Fair Value Gaps (FVG), trendlines, and Harmonic Patterns using image segmentation techniques. Traditional methods rely heavily on manual chart analysis, which can be subjective and time-consuming. By leveraging computer vision and deep learning-based segmentation, this research aims to automate the identification of these patterns, improving accuracy and efficiency in financial market analysis. The proposed model processes financial charts to segment and classify critical price action structures, enabling traders and analysts to make data-driven decisions. Experimental results demonstrate the potential of image segmentation in financial chart analysis, offering a robust tool for pattern detection in trading strategies.

Conflict Of Interest Disclosure.

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I affirm that I have no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to disclose in relation to this research.

1 Introduction

Technical analysis in financial markets heavily depends on identifying key chart patterns that provide insights into future price movements. Manual pattern recognition is both time-consuming and prone to human error. This study addresses these limitations by implementing image segmentation techniques to detect patterns such as Fair Value Gaps (FVG), trendlines, and Harmonic Patterns. By utilizing deep learning methods, this research aims to enhance accuracy, speed, and efficiency in financial chart analysis.

The significance of automated pattern recognition extends beyond individual traders, benefiting institutional investors, algorithmic trading systems, and financial analysts. This paper is structured as follows: Section II presents a literature review on pattern recognition in finance, Section III discusses the methodology, Section IV analyzes experimental results, Section V provides discussions and key observations, and Section VI concludes the study with future recommendations.

Keywords: Financial Market Analysis, Pattern Recognition, Image Segmentation, Technical Analysis, Deep Learning, FVG, Harmonic Patterns, Trend-line.

2 Literature Review

Recent advancements in deep learning and image processing have paved the way for financial chart analysis using artificial intelligence. Studies on Smart Money Concepts (SMC) suggest that FVG plays a crucial role in liquidity dynamics. Harmonic patterns, widely studied in trading strategies, have been modeled using machine learning techniques but lack robust implementation in image segmentation. This study builds upon existing work by integrating deep learning for segmenting these complex patterns effectively.

3 Methodology

The proposed methodology leverages a deep learning based image segmentation approach to detect and classify financial chart patterns. The process is divided into three main stages: data preprocessing, model training, and evaluation. Below, we outline the steps in detail.

3.1 Data Preprocessing

Financial charts were collected from multiple asset classes, including forex, commodities, and indices. Each chart was manually annotated to label FVGs, Harmonic Patterns, and trendlines. The dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets to ensure robust model evaluation.

3.2 Model Architecture

A state-of-the-art deep learning architecture, based on Detectron2, was employed for image segmentation. The model uses a Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) with a ResNet-50 backbone, optimized for detecting small and medium-sized objects in financial charts. Transfer learning was applied to fine-tune the model on the annotated dataset.

3.3 Training Process

The training process involved multiple iterations to optimize model performance:

- **First Iteration:** Initial training with a small dataset (500 images) revealed limitations in pattern recognition due to insufficient data.
- **Second Iteration:** The dataset was expanded to 1859 images, improving the model's ability to detect polygonal shapes like FVGs but struggling with line patterns.

- **Third Iteration:** Additional data augmentation techniques, of file duplication was applied to enhance model generalization.

3.4 Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was evaluated using standard object detection metrics, including Average Precision (AP), AP50, and AP75. These metrics measure the model's accuracy in detecting and classifying patterns at different Intersection-over-Union (IoU) thresholds.

3.5 Dataset Information

3.5.1 FVG

- Train Dataset: 1858 images across EUR/USD, XAU/USD, BTC/USD, USOIL, NVIDIA, NAS-DAQ, and BNKNFTY.
- Valid Dataset: 225 images.
- Test Dataset: 242 images.

3.5.2 Harmonic Patterns

- Train Dataset: 2256 images across EUR/USD, NASDAQ, USOIL, XAU/USD, NVIDIA, BTC/USD, and BNKNFTY.
- Valid Dataset: 281 images.
- Test Dataset: 266 images.

4 Results and Output

This section showcases the results of the proposed methodology, including annotated images and model outputs for FVG and Harmonic

Figure 1: Example of FVG Annotation

Figure 2: Example of FVG Detection

Figure 3: Example of Harmonic Annotation.

Figure 4: Harmonic Pattern **Detection Result**

4.1 Model Outputs

- FVG Model:
 - Lower accuracy overall (AP: 20.41, AP50:44.53, AP75: 15.17)
 - Struggled with small and medium objects
 - Requires further improvement through dataset augmentation

4.2 Table-wise Comparison

Metric	Harmonic Model (bbox)	FVG Model (bbox)
AP	71.33	20.41
AP50	74.39	44.53
AP75	73.89	15.17

5 Future Scope

- Development of an automated system capable of recognizing and classifying various market patterns in real-time, reducing human intervention and improving accuracy.
- Implementation of an advanced system that can automatically assess Fibonacci levels to mark harmonic patterns and classify them into types such as Bat, ABCD, and XABCD.
- Design of an AI-powered decision-making system that leverages detected patterns to provide trading recommendations, enhancing the predictive capabilities of technical analysis.

5.1 Key Observations

- Harmonic Pattern Model:
 - High accuracy for bounding box detection (AP: 71.33, AP50: 74.39, AP75: 73.89)
 - Effective performance in specific category harmonic1.

6 Conclusion

The findings highlight the effectiveness of deep learning in recognizing financial chart patterns. The Harmonic Pattern Model achieved high accuracy, while the FVG model requires further enhancement. Future research should focus on increasing training data, refining annotation strategies, and experimenting with alternative architectures for improved performance.

Figure 5: Additional Harmonic Pattern Detection Result.

Figure 6: Additional FVG Pattern Detection Result

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